

S P A T I A L

D2.2 DEFINE PARAMETERS AND ELEMENTS TO CONSTRUCT ACCOUNTABILITY, RESILIENCE, AND PRIVACY METRICS

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Authors <i>(sorted by alphabetical order of partner names)</i>	Ana Rosa Cavalli (MI), Bartosz Nawrotek (FSC), Claudio Soriente (NEC), David Solans Noguero (TID), Huber Flores (UT), Prachi Bagave (TUD), Manh-Dung Nguyen (MI), Marcus Westburg (TUD), Nicolas Kourtellis (TID), Samuel Marchal (FSC), Setareh Roshan (FSC), Souneil Park (TID), Vinh Hoa La (MI).
Reviewers	Shen Wang (UCD), Dimitris Chatzopoulos (UCD)

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Abstract	This deliverable aims to propose metrics for evaluating the trustworthiness of AI systems, which will provide detailed objectives for efforts to achieving trustworthiness. To comprehensively explore the space and provide practical metrics, we operationalize trustworthiness into three dimensions: accountability, resilience, and privacy. For each dimension, we first develop a ground by studying the existing approaches and the trade-offs they involve, to identify the considerations for the development of metrics. Based on the study, a set of metrics are proposed for each dimension, which can provide insights not only about the degree of trustworthiness but also the potential trade-offs.
Keywords	Trustworthy AI, Metric development, Accountability, Explainability, Resilience, Privacy, Trade-off analysis.

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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SPATIAL project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is part of Work Package 2 of the SPATIAL project, which focuses on defining metrics for understanding the trustworthiness of machine learning (ML) systems. Whereas the previous Deliverable 2.1 lay a basis that captures the requirements for designing accountable and resilient AI methods, this deliverable provides detailed objectives through a set of metrics for developing trustworthy AI systems. We believe the proposal of these metrics is important as trustworthiness of AI is becoming critical. AI technologies are broadly entering diverse real-life applications and services, interacting with people, supporting personalization, and even being employed for infrastructural systems as well. Moreover, as the main focus of the literature on evaluating AI systems has been on the performance aspects, research on trustworthiness metrics is pertinent and necessary more than ever. The metrics proposed in this deliverable will provide detailed directions for achieving trustworthiness goals.

The deliverable approaches to comprehensive explore the trustworthiness and at the same time to provide practical metrics that can be implemented and used in real AI systems. For this purpose, we operationalize the concept of trustworthiness into three dimensions: accountability¹, resilience, and privacy. The three dimensions are identified based on the ground of requirement analyses which were conducted for the Deliverables 1.1 and 2.1, and they broadly cover the fundamental aspects of trustworthiness in a less redundant manner.

For each dimension, we approach to propose the metrics in two steps: first, by exploring the factors/parameters of existing approaches to obtain insights about the considerations for the proposal of the metrics; second, a study of the trade-offs that are involved in the identified considerations to clarify what the metrics should reveal.

As for accountability, we explore the key factors discussed in the literature and important related initiatives, then we discuss how they commonly share explainability as the main construct. The potential trade-offs of having accountability and explainability with respect to accuracy and privacy is followed. The resilience dimension is explored considering the main attack types to ML systems including model poisoning, model evasion, and model stealing. Existing approaches to defend or assess the vulnerability from those attacks are studied, and the trade-offs with accuracy, privacy, and explainability are discussed. Lastly, the privacy dimension broadly surveys different approaches to protect personal data, and summarizes their trade-offs with utility, resources, and user experience. Based on the study of each dimension and the discussion of the trade-offs, a set of metrics are proposed and described in detail considering how they could be practically applied particularly considering the use cases of SPATIAL.

¹ As for accountability, this deliverable views explainability as the key means to achieving it, which is consistent to the previous deliverables 1.1 and 2.1. Later in this document we put both terms together in order to avoid confusion.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASL	Average Number of Words per Sentence
AUC	Area Under Curve
AUROC	Area under Receiver operating characteristics curve
AWL	Average Number of Syllables per Word
CLEVER	Cross Lipschitz Extreme Value for nEtwork Robustness
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DNN	Deep Neural Network
ER	Empirical Robustness
FL	Federated Learning
FRES	Flesch Reading Ease
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet Of Things
LIME	Local Interpretable Model Agnostic Explanation
LS	Loss Sensitivity
ML	Machine Learning
MPC	Secure Multi-party Computation
PII	Personal Identifiable Information
RF	Random Forests
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SVM	Support Vector Machines
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
XAI	Explainable AI

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable builds upon the previous deliverables (D1.1 and D2.1) that surveyed the requirements for the development of secure and trustworthy AI, by identifying the key parameters and trade-offs of the techniques for secure and trustworthy AI and proposing metrics for evaluation of the techniques. As described well in the previous deliverables, the need to assess trustworthiness of AI technologies is growing as the use of AI is expanding to crucial infrastructure domains such as energy, emergency communication, cyber security, Internet of Things (IoT), 5G, automotive, or railway. Moreover, the use of AI technologies for personalized and interactive systems are also continuously increasing and it becomes important to hold them trustworthy from the perspective of the users.

The need to understand the trustworthiness is relatively under-explored since the main objective in the design and development of AI applications and AI-based systems has been to achieve the highest possible accuracy in the classification and prediction capabilities of the underlying models. Consequently, approaches for understanding and evaluating them have evolved in that regards as well. As the use of AI becomes wider as described above, methods for characterization and evaluation should consider the aspects of trustworthiness, such as explainability, resilience, privacy, fairness, etc.

This deliverable aims to mind this gap, and explores the design choices and evaluation methods specific to the trustworthiness of AI methods. We center the exploration around the three areas that we believe to broadly cover the fundamental aspects of trustworthiness in a less redundant manner: accountability and explainability, resilience, and privacy.

Accountability and explainability, which we operationalize as how easily AI models can be understood, is becoming more crucial to trustworthiness especially because the recent high-performing Machine Learning (ML) algorithms like Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) or Random Forests (RF) suffer from a lack of transparency and explainability. Due to their high complexity, the decision-making process and the underlying functions of many algorithms is hard to understand by human operators or auditors. As a result, such ML algorithms are often perceived as opaque black-boxes, and they motivate principled ways of explaining the behaviors of the ML-based systems, also means to assess the degree of explainability of them.

Resilience is another aspect that is becoming more important as adoption of AI increases in various infrastructures and services, and with the emergence of new adversarial ML attacks which broadens the attack surface and introduce new vulnerabilities and security risks for ML-based systems. Considering the potential severe impact than an attack can make, it is necessary to explore systematic ways of designing resilient AI methods and assessing the degree of resilience.

It is also evident that the use of personal data in AI systems will increase, and AI systems will be continuously used for personalization and interact with users more closely. At the same time, new approaches for privacy preserving AI methods are being developed and they give insights about the parameters of the design space and the necessary metrics for privacy.

1.1 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document is the next step from the previous deliverables that explore the requirements and design guidelines for modern system architectures based on accountable AI, and we focus on identifying the criteria for understanding the trustworthiness and proposing metrics for the purpose. This deliverable is also intended to produce inputs for the upcoming tasks of SPATIAL, particularly the use case development efforts of Work Package 5. Therefore, this deliverable reflects the areas and requirements explored in the previous deliverables and the proposed metrics include the ones that are tailored to the use cases.

As mentioned this deliverable selects and covers three areas: accountability and explainability, resilience, and privacy. Precisely, this document has two goals: first to provide an overview of the key properties that affect the trustworthiness; second, to propose a set of metrics that reflect the identified properties. We make effort to make the overview of the properties associated to trustworthiness as comprehensive as possible, and at the same time, also to keep the metrics detailed enough so they can be practically used in AI systems and applications. In summary this deliverable will make the following contributions:

- Review of the terms accountability and explainability, resilience, and privacy in order to clarify the scope of the exploration.
- A detailed breakdown of the concept of accountability and identification of the key elements for evaluation.
- A study of the trade-offs that accountability has in AI systems.
- A review of the methods for evaluation of AI system resilience regarding common attack types.
- A study of the trade-offs that resilience has in AI systems.
- A review of the design choices and parameters of solutions for privacy in AI systems.
- A study of the trade-offs that privacy has in AI systems.
- A set of metrics for evaluating AI systems with respect to the three studied dimensions.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The remainder of this deliverable document is structured as follows: In Section 2, we review our definition of the three areas to clarify the scope of our study (i.e., accountability and explainability, resilience, and privacy). Based on this, Section 3 explores each area. For each area, we organize the study in two parts: first, we discuss the factors, design choices, and parameters that affect the trustworthiness of AI systems; second, we discuss the trade-offs involved in the identified elements. Section 4 dives into the proposed metrics based on the discussion made in Section 3. Finally, we will summarize the main messages and conclude the deliverable in Section 5.

2 TERMINOLOGY

In this section, we clarify the terms we use that define the three main areas that we explore in this deliverable. Since a broader discussion of the concepts and terms of the whole SPATIAL project is already presented in the previous deliverable 1.1, we revisit and summarize the parts that are key to building the context of this deliverable.

2.1 ACCOUNTABILITY AND EXPLAINABILITY

As defined in deliverable 1.1, by accountability of an AI system, we refer to the system being able to explain and justify the conducts, and having the affected people understand the reason behind the conducts and identify the people or organisation responsible for.

We use the term explainability together with accountability to describe the explored area, as we see explainability as the key for achieving accountability. By explainability, we refer to the objective of AI systems or techniques to dissect the complex logic involved in the decision process of a model, such that it is possible to determine the causes that lead to that decision. In the context of SPATIAL, explainability specifically concerns AI models that work in a black-box manner and that can be easily biased by programming errors from developers or quality of the data used in the training process. Thus the explainability we consider is the ability to explain an AI model's behavior with the help of its feature space, training records, targets, and the machine learning algorithm itself, which ultimately helps users build trust on the AI model.

2.2 RESILIENCE

The second area we explore, resilience, refers to the capability of a system to recover from disruptive events and attacks. As described in the previous deliverable 1.1, we follow the synthesized definition where resilience is defined as the "ability of an information system to reduce the magnitude, impact, and/or duration of disruptive events or unknown changes in the operating environment (including deliberate attacks, accidents and naturally occurring threats or incidents) by *a*) anticipating and preparing for such events (e.g., through risk management, contingency and continuity planning); *b*) being able to withstand and adapt to attacks, adverse conditions or other stress and potential disruptions, and continuing to operate while maintaining essential and required operational capabilities; and *c*) recovering full operational capabilities after such a disruption in a time frame consistent with mission needs."

2.3 PRIVACY

As for the area of privacy, this document follows the same definition provided in the deliverable 1.1, which is focused on data privacy and is based on GDPR. To sum up, data privacy is defined as empowering the users to make their own decisions about who can process their data and for what purpose. An important concept that is coupled with data privacy is personal data, which refers to any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person. Here the personal data not only recognizes the information that can identify a natural person (such

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as address, identity number, etc.) but also any data generated by the person (such as for example phone call logs, website access logs and purchase history), and also any meta-data generated from such data (such as patterns extracted from the logs, labels assigned to the person by a machine learning algorithm etc.).

3 PARAMETERS & TRADE-OFF ANALYSIS FOR METRIC DEVELOPMENT

This section broadly explores each area in order to identify the considerations for metric development. Every area is covered in a subsection, and for each area we first study available approaches and their parameters or key elements, which leads to the considerations for metric development. We later discuss the trade-offs involved with the area in order to discuss how the considerations should be reflected in the metrics.

3.1 ACCOUNTABILITY

Accountability is often necessary when an entity in power does not behave as expected, causing a need to understand the reason behind the entity's actions and identify the cause, such as the responsible person or organisation [2]. Since AI is also growing as a socio-technical system, having applications in critical domains like healthcare, autonomous driving, and judicial sector, it has high impacts on various aspects of our lives. Due to the increased development and reliance on black-box models in AI systems and research, there is a high demand for algorithmic accountability and calls for such has been raised by the EU [3] as well as the US [4].

3.1.1 FACTORS OF ACCOUNTABILITY & EXPLAINABILITY

The definition of the term accountability is most widely accepted as 'the obligation to explain and justify conduct' [2], [5]. In addition Boven [2], defines accountability as a relationship between an actor and a forum, where the actor is obligated to explain and justify his actions to the forum and also faces consequences of the judgement from them.

Approaches to Achieving Accountability: At a high level, general approaches to achieving accountability focus on understanding of how an AI system works. For example, a method for accountability in AI systems can involve transparency in all processes, including data collection, data processing, modelling choices, training quality and releasing source code. Another method is to build (post hoc) interpretable models that is easy for users to understand how an AI system works, such as visualization, classic statistical methods, and algorithmic methods. Apart from those methods discussed above, [6] introduced a different method for accountability, named Empirical Performance (Pre-Market and Post-Market), focusing on empirical evidence, especially for the AI system towards satisfying certain objectives such as safety, fairness, or performance. For example, the pre-market safety process for an autonomous vehicle may involve measuring certain kinds of safety violations in a variety of settings in a continuous manner. This performance will also be evaluated in the post-market process through reporting systems for adversarial events [6].

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AI governance is another promising initiative toward accountability. AI governance is “the process of defining policies and establishing accountability to guide the creation and deployment of AI systems in an organization”, according to [7]. AI governance processes provides transparency into how AI systems are created and deployed by monitoring data on AI models in a responsible and governed manner. As big companies often scale their use of AI, they increasingly need to implement their governance in the whole lifecycle of the AI systems. Clearly, AI governance is critical and indispensable for all enterprises to develop and deploy AI. For instance, IBM provided a model focusing on the governance of the AI lifecycle [7]. This model consists of 6 levels of increasing the AI lifecycle governance maturity level to ensure AI systems satisfy the requirements of the business, from level 0 (no AI lifecycle governance) to level 5 (fully automated AI lifecycle governance), as follows:

- Level 0 - No AI lifecycle governance
- Level 1 - AI policies available to guide AI lifecycle governance:
- Level 2 - Common set of metrics to govern AI lifecycle
- Level 3 - Enterprise data and AI catalog
- Level 4 - Automated validation and monitoring
- Level 5 - Fully automated AI lifecycle governance

This model provides a better understanding of the value of AI governance, and helps organizations determine at which level their AI lifecycle governance is to enhance further their governance.

The European Commission [3] has also enlisted accountability as one of the key requirements for AI development. The four major elements to ensure accountability mentioned in the guidelines are:

- **Auditability:** The systems should facilitate the ability to trace their actions.
- **Minimizing and reporting negative impact:** The systems should ensure both minimization of risk of negative impact as well as reporting thereof should it occur.
- **Documenting trade-offs:** Any trade-offs to achieve accountability should be well documented.
- **Ability to redress:** In case of any mishap, immediate corrective actions should be conducted.

Conceptualising algorithmic accountability for AI: One of the most important features of accountability in AI research and development is the ability to reason the outcomes of an AI system. Explainable AI (XAI), as a growing area of research, builds on the principle of accountability by using explainability as a means of understanding the AI algorithms and also provide reasons for its decision making, thereby creating a relationship between the AI system (actor) and users/stakeholders (forum). In the Figure 1, we conceptualise the various factors responsible for algorithmic accountability as drawn from the literature. Interpretability and transparency are used for gaining insights and understanding algorithms decision making. Whereas causality, reviewability, and auditability are used to explain the AI functioning to domain experts or authorities judging the AI functionality.

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FIGURE 1. FACTORS OF ACCOUNTABILITY

Causality refers to the study of causes and effects of a system. In context of AI, this corresponds to finding out the causes behind why a particular decision was given by the algorithm. Current explainability methods find these causes either by explaining the whole model (global explanations) or by explaining a particular case (local explanation) [8]. These studies have also been extended in a way that the users can relate these explanations in the application context. The study of causality in human reasoning has also led to an increased interest in structuring explanations as counterfactuals, which gives contrastive explanations in the form of “what if” conditions [9]. Thus it helps to generate actionable steps which can lead to desirable outcomes and can lead to interventional recourses [7].

Reviewability and Auditability: Auditability refers to the process of record keeping, logging and documenting of processes in a system, which can be used for reviewing the system behaviour for desirable attributes and legal compliance. Reviewability, in a similar vein, can be defined as a holistic and systemic approach to accountability via an iterative process of review, feedback, and revision [6].

Interpretability and Transparency: Interpretability is defined as ‘the ability to explain in understandable terms. In regards to contexts involving ML systems, there is an added qualifier to this term that ‘understandable’ is directed toward being understandable to a human [10], [11], [12]. Further, it is inferred as the cognitive effort required by humans to provide meaning to the way they understand the workings of an algorithm [13], [14]. In the context of XAI, interpretability is used in contexts of humans understanding the processes of black-box models, and thus bringing about transparency. Transparency as a term is often found accompanying interpretability in XAI literature, but technical definitions are less frequent. In Cliniciu & Hastie [15], transparency is described as a blanket concept to which intelligibility, interpretability and explainability are facets. In addition, transparency is identified as a key component in improving user trust in a system [16].

Responsibility: Responsibility is referred to as the willingness of an actor to act in a transparent, fair and equitable way. This is a non-analytical factor, but can be used by the authorities for drawing conclusions while performing accountability [2]. As in human decision making systems, AI decision making systems can also face the problem of many hands [17]. In this context, multiple inputs, data points, architectures, and parties providing the data could be held accountable for any given event. Thus, defining clear responsibility can help resolve such issues.

3.1.2 DISCUSSION OF TRADE-OFFS

Accountability vs. Accuracy

More complex systems are capable of modelling complex decision functions more accurately but are less likely to be interpretable by human. For example, deep learning techniques are accurate, but provide no explanations, while more simple, understandable techniques, such as rule-based models, tend to produce less accurate prediction. Ideally, the model outputs and explanations must be interpretable and understandable for not only AI model developers but also non-specialists users. Clearly, explainability and accuracy are both needed in certain AI based systems. On one hand, we can use explainable models, such as decision trees, where domain experts can easily interpret the model's predictions and gain insights into the outputs. On the other hand, more sophisticated AI models, such as deep neural networks, may need to be applied for complex use cases like object recognition or facial recognition. Thus, there is a tradeoff between model interpretability and performance, meaning that making AI models more understandable for users could eventually reduce the accuracy of their decisions [18]. AI explainability becomes a double-edged sword: while more explainability enhances the opportunity to verify and contest a decision, it would also increase the probability of error or degrade the quality of the AI models. In some cases, providing a clear explanation is very challenging because it is difficult to explain specifically how bits of the image were mapped to the object or face in the AI image recognition system due to the model complexity. As more explainable AI systems may be less accurate, the person affected by that decision may therefore not necessarily consider increased explainability a good thing. We therefore need to explore how people would make the trade-off between these contradictory concepts to make decisions about them.

Developing XAI models or adding a new layer of interpretability on top of complex AI models can reduce the trade-off between accuracy and explainability. For example, many XAI tools and platforms, developed by big companies like Google, IBM, provide insights to users on how much each feature contributes to a model's prediction. Nevertheless, XAI still has limitations, especially in explaining sophisticated AI models with millions of parameters. For instance, LIME - one of the most popular XAI methods can highlight the key features extracted in image classification problem using CNN, but it is not fully transparent because it only produce explanations after a decision has been made by AI models.

We discuss some potential of AI model developments to achieve an optimal balance between the interpretability and performance of ML models. Firstly, not every decision problem in our real life, especially in healthcare [2], requires modelling of a complex function, because sometimes simple models, that are easily understandable by users, can also produce similar precision results. In such cases, accurate results are more important for AI based systems than model explanations. Secondly, AI model developers could consider incorporating a simpler model alongside a more complex one and show both output models to users [19]. Thus, we can avoid the trade-off between accuracy and explainability. Thirdly, we can use some alternative guarantees, such as algorithmic fairness or data bias, to reduce the need of explainability of AI models. Finally, depending on the end user's requirements and concrete scenarios, we may consider to achieve the goal of explainability without necessarily having fully explained AI models.

Accountability vs. Anonymity (Privacy)

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Balance between anonymity and accountability is a major concern in many privacy-based systems, such as web-based transactions [20], public administrations [21] or AI-based applications. Indeed, the quality of AI-based applications really depend on how good the datasets are in the training phase. The protection of users' privacy when applying machine learning techniques is an important factor in the acceptance and use of AI-based systems in our life, such as autonomous vehicles and clinical diagnosis. While anonymity refers to the absence of identifying information associated with an interaction, accountability is required to make entities within the system responsible for their acts. Current applications that provide full anonymity lack accountability, thus the possibility of misuse and the lack of controllability exist. Therefore, anonymity and accountability are both needed in certain applications and more importantly, we need to consider the trade-off between these contradictory concepts. We here focus on the trade-off with privacy in the context of accountability, recognizing that there are privacy solutions (e.g., differential privacy) developed to address this limitation. A separate discussion about the privacy solutions and the trade-offs they have can be found in Section 3.3.

Considering an example of the AI applications in healthcare, they need patients' data to improve the early detection of diseases including cancer and retinopathies. The first set of concerns includes access, use and control of patient data in private hands. Another set of concerns relates to the external risk of privacy breaches through AI-driven methods, for example new algorithms could reidentify anonymised patient health data, thus violate the anonymity of the users. However, it also reduces the quality of insights from a dataset, hindering from deriving all possible values from dataset insights.

Accountability vs. Resilience

In addition to the privacy concern, accountability also entails risks in terms of resilience of AI systems. Providing explanations about the logic of AI-based systems can potentially increase the risk of unintentionally disclosing private information in the process. Transparency and interpretability may also make attackers easier to infer private information about the AI models or the individuals whose personal data are used in the training data. Attackers can easily steal or replicate the performance of other proprietary models. Such cases point to another trade-off, which is between accountability and resilience. We revisit this trade-off in more detail in Section 3.2.2. Organisations need to monitor the latest research, include standards and policy guidelines and apply practical methods for mitigating these risks.

3.2 RESILIENCE

Properly securing ML systems requires knowledge about their security posture at a given point in time. Methods to assess and quantify the resilience/vulnerability against ML-specific attacks enable to document this security posture. The results of these assessments are useful for several purposes:

- Evidence of sufficient protection in case of successful attack
- Quantify the security risk (in correlation with threats and impact of successful attacks)
- Prioritize security investment to fix the most severe vulnerabilities identified
- Use assessment results and knowledge to fix identified vulnerabilities

3.2.1 EXISTING METHODS AND METRICS TO RESILIENCE

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In this section, we present the main approaches and metrics to quantify the resilience of ML systems against poisoning, evasion and model stealing attacks. These approaches are divided in two categories. First, methods to assess the vulnerability of already defined and implemented ML systems, which is our main focus. Second, approaches that modify the design or implementation of ML systems in order to provide a certified level of resilience.

3.2.1 Assessments Methods & Metrics for Vulnerability

Model poisoning

The need to assess and measure the vulnerability of ML models against poisoning attacks is an important precondition for allowing reliable and accountable deployment of ML models. In contrast to attack detection and prevention, vulnerability assessment aims to uncover vulnerabilities before an attack happens to enable the application of prevention strategies and increase security.

The main quantifiable parameters of a vulnerability score should be 1) *poisoned percentage*, which is the upper bound on the percentage of samples, out of a training dataset, which can be modified by an attacker, and 2) *score decrease*, which measures the decrease of a performance score between clean and poisoned models. The performance score function should be based on the defender's preference, commonly accuracy or F1-score.

The definition of the vulnerability score depends on a careful, task-oriented selection of the parameters. In general, we should consider what is the allowed change on the input. Frequently, for the image domain, it will be an imperceptible change to the brightness of pixels bounded by a ball with radius R . In the cyber security domain, for a malware classification system for instance, it may be any change to the sample, which doesn't impact the malware functionality.

For a classification task, another factor having an impact on the vulnerability score value is the attacker's capability, e.g., whether an adversary can change the samples' labels or not. A realistic scenario where such capability is given to the adversary would be during the outsourcing of a model's training to external services.

The *poisoned percentage* and ability to modify the training data can be qualified as the attacker's constraints (or attacker's capability). Their purpose is to define, what are the allowed perturbations, that an attacker can introduce to the data during training or inference time.

Apart from the attacker's constraints, we should consider the goal of the attack. According to the taxonomy proposed in [22], we can mainly distinguish integrity (backdoor attack) and availability violations during poisoning attacks. In backdoor attacks, the *score decrease* is computed based on a subset of samples on which a *trigger* (chosen by the attacker) is applied. In contrast, in traditional availability poisoning attacks, the *score decrease* is computed on a set of samples representative the whole data distribution.

To the best of our knowledge, there is no generic metric for vulnerability assessment against poisoning attacks yet. However, a few methods have been proposed for certifying the robustness of ML models against, e.g., backdoor attacks [23] and label modification attacks [24]. These methods guarantee a minimum level of accuracy for a given ML model subjected to a given poisoning attack. This minimum accuracy is inferred based upon a ball of a certain radius

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R, so it does not apply to any ML systems. Also, these certification methods are often incompatible and there is no framework allowing to certify the robustness of a model targeted by both backdoor and label modification attacks with a single accuracy guarantee. The usefulness of these certification methods depends on the level of accuracy being certified: if it is too low, the provided guarantee is not useful. Consequently, methods for assessing the vulnerability of ML models against poisoning attack and providing a tighter bound is necessary.

Model evasion

ML models are vulnerable against evasion attacks using adversarial examples, which make the model change its original prediction to an incorrect one. There has been a great amount of research on adversarial attack algorithms in different domains and according to new threat models. One major purpose of these studies is to improve the robustness of machine learning models against adversarial examples by developing appropriate defense methods. Robustness analysis is a key element in evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed defenses. Such analysis allows ML experts to understand how models perform under attack and make well-informed design decisions when it comes to improving their security.

To evaluate the robustness of a machine learning model against adversarial examples, it is required to define a quantifiable robustness metric. A typical robustness metric is the attack *success rate* which correlates to the degradation in model *accuracy* under the attack. Another primary metric widely used in the state-of-the-art [25],[26] is the minimum *perturbation budget* required to introduce a successful attack, i.e., cause a misclassification. *Perturbation budget* is calculated by measuring the norm of the difference between the original and adversarial sample. This metric also relates to the sensitivity of the classifier to changes in the inputs. An additional metric used for evaluating the effectiveness of evasion attack, in a blackbox setting, and model robustness is the *query budget* corresponding to the number of queries required to generate a successful adversarial example.

While these metrics can be considered independently, their correlated impact on classifiers robustness is often studied. For instance, specifying a limited query and perturbation budget, may degrade the effectiveness of attacks and improve classifiers robustness. There are two primary evaluation curves widely used as evaluation means in this respect [27]: 1) attack *success rate* versus *perturbation budget* and 2) attack *success rate* versus *query budget*. Both of these curves, provide a global understanding of the model robustness and the attack effectiveness.

In addition to the above metrics, there are several non-quantifiable factors which impact the robustness of the classifier and effectiveness of adversarial attacks.

Knowledge about the ML model: The knowledge of adversary about the model impacts its robustness against adversarial examples. The vulnerability against evasion attacks increases when a model is accessible in a whitebox setting and if it is differentiable. It decreases when the model is isolated and available as blackbox

Granularity of predictions: This factor is only relevant in blackbox settings, where the adversary requires access to the output of the classifier. Fine-grained predictions make evasion attacks faster and more successful than coarse grained predictions.

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In the following, we present three example approaches proposed for evaluating the robustness of classifiers against evasion attacks relying on adversarial examples.

The *Empirical Robustness (ER)* metric [28] corresponds to the effectiveness of a specific attack against a classifier with respect to a particular data set. The effectiveness of the attack can be restricted by a limited *perturbation budget*, which degrades the effectiveness of the attack. As a result, a classifier is more robust against attacks which require a larger *perturbation budget*.

ER measures the average *perturbation budget* required by an attack to generate a successful adversarial example. A larger ER score suggest a larger required *perturbation budget* by the attack and therefore a more robust classifier. ER score is typically taken into consideration in correlation with the attack *success rate*. With a similar *success rate*, a classifier is more robust against attacks with a larger ER score.

With ρ and X being a particular attack and test set respectively, the ER metric is computed as the minimum amount of perturbation (calculated using a given p norm) in the set of successful samples. Assuming I as the set containing indices of successful samples, ER score is computed according to the following formula.

$$ER(\rho, X) = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \frac{\|\rho(x_i) - x_i\|_p}{\|x_i\|_p}$$

The *Loss Sensitivity (LS)* metric is an attack-agnostic metric relying on the smoothness of the classifier function, i.e., the degree to which the classifier output changes with respects to the changes in the input. LS quantifies this smoothness, by estimating the average sensitivity of the classifier loss function. Therefore, it relies on the properties of the classifier and its loss function. A low LS score corresponds to a classifier robust against evasion.

LS score can be measured by estimating the Lipschitz continuity constant of the loss function. A function is Lipschitz continuous if and only if its first derivative is bounded. The smallest of such bound is called Lipschitz continuity constant. Lipschitz continuity constant for the classifier loss function L can be estimated based on the gradients of the classifier logits [29] according to the following formula.

$$LS(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\nabla \mathcal{L}(x_i, y_i)\|_2$$

The *Cross Lipschitz Extreme Value for nEtnetwork Robustness (CLEVER)* is an attack-agnostic metric for measuring the robustness of neural networks classifiers [30]. This metric estimates a universal lower bound on the minimum *perturbation budget* required to successfully craft an adversarial example. In other words, any adversarial perturbation smaller than such a bound does not change the classifier predictions and fails evasion. By defining this bound, the CLEVER score guarantees the robustness of a classifier in an l_p -ball with radius R in the neighborhood of the original sample. A large CLEVER score indicates robustness against a larger range of adversarial perturbations.

Under the assumption of Lipschitz continuity of the classification function, this lower bound can be derived as the Lipschitz continuity constant for the gradients of classifier's logits. This also corresponds to the maximum norm of gradient differences, and it is calculated by randomly

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selecting perturbations from a uniform distribution within the l_p -ball with radius R around the original sample. Despite its computational efficiency and strong theoretical guarantees in providing a lower bound for minimum *perturbation budget*, CLEVER score relies on the properties of neural networks, and it may not be applicable to other classifier types.

Model stealing

Model stealing attacks threaten the confidentiality and intellectual property of ML models. It is necessary to know if and how a given ML model can be stolen by a client having access to its query API. So far, studies have shown that every model is vulnerable to some extent to model stealing attacks, and completely preventing these attacks is nearly impossible [31],[32]. However, the cost and effort required for an attacker to steal an ML model depends on many factors, and under some conditions, attacks can be unpractical [32].

To the best of our knowledge, no vulnerability assessment method or metric exist to evaluate the vulnerability against model stealing attacks. Thus, the recommended approach would be to launch diverse model stealing attacks against a target ML model, and to evaluate their effectiveness, as it is done to evaluate the resilience against evasion attacks for instance. The quantifiable metrics used to evaluate the effectiveness of a model stealing attack are 1) the number of requests required to steal a given ML model and 2) the quality of the stolen model. The quality of the stolen model can be evaluated according to diverse metrics depending on the goal of the stealing attack, e.g., accuracy of the stolen model compared to the target, agreement in predictions between target and stolen model [33]. A vulnerability score can be computed based on this number of requests and quality metrics. A low number of required requests, a high accuracy and a high agreement in predictions translate to a high vulnerability against model stealing attacks. On the other hand, a high number of required requests, a low accuracy and a low agreement in predictions translate to a low vulnerability against model stealing attacks. A global severity score could be computed by recording and aggregating the vulnerability scores obtained from empirically running different model stealing attacks against the ML model we want to assess.

Besides the quantifiable number of queries and quality of the stolen model, several other non-quantifiable factors influence the effectiveness of model stealing attacks and thus the vulnerability against them [33]. These must also be considered when assessing this vulnerability:

- **Required granularity of predictions:** The vulnerability against stealing attacks typically increase when predictions become fine-grained and leak more information about the model.
- **Knowledge about target ML model:** Knowing the type, structure, task, etc. of the model to steal reduces the search space for the stealing attack and increases the vulnerability against it.
- **Access to training data:** If the attacker has knowledge and access to the same, or similar, data as the one used to train the target ML model, it can generate better queries to steal the model. It increases vulnerability against stealing attacks.
- **Detectability of stealing attack queries:** Different stealing attacks generate different type of queries. Some of them are highly synthetic and much different from what the

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target model expects as input while others are not. In the latter case, the vulnerability is increased because it is difficult to detect an attack that relies on such queries.

3.2.2 DISCUSSION OF TRADE-OFFS

Resilience vs. Accuracy

The security property of a system is often in contention with its performance and usability properties. Considering machine learning systems, an increased resilience against adversarial machine learning attacks often comes at the price of accuracy. For instance, the most effective defense against evasion attacks, namely adversarial training, reduces the accuracy of models they protect [34]. Thus, the assessment of resilience for an ML system must be combined with a parallel assessment of the ML system's accuracy to ensure that improvements obtain in one property do not come at the price of degrading another property to an unacceptable level.

Resilience vs. Privacy

Security and privacy properties can also conflict between each other in an ML system. It has been shown that methods to increase the resilience of ML models against model evasion attacks can compromise the privacy of the data used to train these models. For instance, the popular adversarial training defense makes ML models more vulnerable against data inference attacks compromising the confidentiality of training data [35]. Privacy and resilience properties must be jointly evaluated in order to ensure both these properties are preserved. We here focus on the trade-off with privacy in the context of resilience. A separate discussion about the other trade-offs of privacy solutions can be found in Section 3.3.2.

Resilience vs. Explainability

As we briefly described about the trade-off between accountability and resilience in Section 3.1.2, a common characteristic of adversarial machine learning attacks is that their effectiveness increases as the attacker's knowledge about the ML model and its decision process increase. Consequently, the obfuscation of ML models' decision process, by making it a blackbox, is an effective way to increase the resilience of ML systems against adversarial ML attacks [36].

Explainability reveals the decision process of blackbox ML models, thereby uncovering helpful information to an attacker. It has been shown that the information produced by explainable ML techniques can be leveraged to design more effective black-box attacks [37]. The effectiveness of membership inference, model extraction, poisoning, and evasion attacks increases against black-box ML models augmented with explainability.

When building and assessing the resilience of an ML system, one must consider and prioritize all the desired properties of this system, e.g., resilience, accuracy, privacy, etc. All these properties must be assessed at the same time because of their co-dependence and none of them can be assessed in isolation. A prioritization list can be used to support the assessment in order to strike a desired trade-off to meet all the system requirements.

3.3 PRIVACY

With the increasing awareness on the importance of personal data and privacy, various approaches, frameworks, and technologies are being developed. In this section, we review major approaches that cover different privacy scenarios including differential privacy, federated

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learning, trusted execution, secure multiparty computation, and identify their parameters in order to provide a comprehensive discussion.

3.3.1 PARAMETERS AND METRICS TO PRIVACY

Differential Privacy

Differential privacy deals with the problem of deanonymization in the scenarios where data that includes sensitive information about people (such as medical records or census) has to be processed or shared while privacy of individuals have to be preserved. Even if the data is pre-processed to drop personal identifiable information (PII), studies [38] [39] have shown how individuals can be identified using the other fields available in the data. In general, the more fields available and the more possible entries for the fields exist in the data set, the possibility to identify a particular row as a unique person increases.

The idea of differential privacy is to deliberately add noise to the data so that the data still preserves the characteristics and provide accurate response to the queries still while allowing *plausible deniability*. For example, a differential privacy mechanism can go through the data records (where a record corresponds to an individual), and replace a certain portion with a randomized records (whose fields have random values). As a record of an individual could be either a true record of the person or a randomized record, the individual has plausible deniability about whether the record is his or her information.

The key parameter of such differential privacy mechanism is ϵ . The parameter defines the bound of how much a differential privacy mechanism hides the difference between a certain row being included in the dataset and not. In brief, an ϵ differential privacy mechanism M guarantees $div[M[D] \parallel M[D']] \leq \epsilon$ where D is a dataset and D' is the same dataset but without a certain record of D , and div is a measure of divergence between probability distributions, such as the Renyi divergence. If a mechanism is 0-differential private, it guarantees complete privacy since there is no effect of the missing record from D' . For example, the corresponding individual of the record missing from D' can completely deny the existence in the dataset D . There are multiple mechanisms used for differential privacy, including the Laplace mechanism, exponential mechanism, and the Gaussian mechanism to name a few. We do not go into the details of each mechanism as it goes beyond the scope of this deliverable.

Despite having the parameter ϵ , it is still important to understand how well a dataset produced by a differential privacy mechanism will support the required analyses. As the answer to this problem in practice depends on the type of analyses, there isn't a general metric. Researchers and practitioners have used several methods. First, the summary statistics of the anonymized data is a simple measure to understand the utility of the anonymized data compared to the original data. For example, the United States Census Bureau [40] has reported various measures including the mean absolute error, root mean squared error, coefficient of variation, etc. Second, distributional distance between the original data and the anonymized data also gives sense about the utility. For example, Chi-squared tests can be used for categorical variables and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) tests can be used for continuous variables.

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Federated Learning (FL)

Federated learning is emerging as a promising technology to build machine learning models in a decentralized, privacy-preserving fashion. The technology addresses a different aspect of privacy from the concerns of differential privacy: it protects personal data from being collected and processed in centralized systems. Federated learning can be also enhanced by combining it with differential privacy mechanisms.

In order to understand the key parameters of federated learning, there are a number of important environmental characteristics that need to be discussed. A federated learning environment typically assumes massively distributed client devices, whose connection is intermittent and slow. As such, the availability of the data for training a model is highly dynamic, depending on the hour, day, and location of the devices. As a consequence, the devices that contribute to the training process is often non-representative of the population.

The federated aggregation, is a process that iteratively builds the ultimate model on top of this environmental dynamicity. In brief, individual devices build a local model with the data available on the device, then the local models are shared with the centralized system on the server. This aggregation is repeated iteratively.

Therefore, the main parameters of federated learning are related to dealing with the environmental dynamicity and aggregation. We summarize the major parameters below.

- Set of devices & fraction of devices participating in an aggregation round: these determine the scale of the model and affects the diversity and representativeness of the model.
- Number of global rounds: the number of iterations required to build the ultimate global model.
- Model dependent parameters for local training: Number of local rounds, batch size, learning rate.

As federated learning models are built upon a distributed environment, there are multiple aspects in the evaluation of them. Firstly, the evaluation should consider the accuracy of the model. The evaluation could look into the accuracy of the local models and the global model separately, and often the accuracy of the global model is compared to the accuracy which would be achieved by a centralized ML system (which collects all data to the centralized server). Secondly, as federated learning models involve numerous client devices and interact with them, the evaluation should also measure the communication cost, which could be measured by counting the communication rounds and the amount of data transferred for building the model. The evaluation should also consider the total time required to building the model, from initialization, training, to validation of the model. Lastly, due to the uncertainty of data availability for training, the models face the non-IID issue of data. Thus, the evaluation could also explore the accuracy assuming the non-IID data.

Trusted Execution

A Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) enables secure execution of arbitrary code on untrusted hosts. Namely, the code running in a TEE is shielded from other applications running on the same host and from privileged software like the operating system. This is usually achieved by extending the Instruction Set Architecture of a processor architecture with a number of special instructions that user-code can invoke and that are directly handled by the

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host hardware/firmware. A number of academic [41], [42] and industrial TEEs [43], [44], [45] are available, being Intel SGX [44] and AMD SEV [45] the most popular TEEs for workstations and servers. TEE applications enjoy confidential runtime memory, encrypted and authenticated storage, and integrity of the execution flow. Further, a TEE application can attest to an external party. That is, a remote party can verify that a known piece of code is running within a TEE on a remote untrusted host. An exemplary use-case of TEEs is the one where a party owns an application that deals with sensitive data but lacks the computing resources to run such application. TEEs allow that party to run its application on an untrusted cloud while retaining the confidentiality of the data handled by the application. Therefore, TEEs are particularly suited for AI applications that handle sensitive data (e.g., e-health, e-finance, etc.) as they allow both data and model providers to execute the application in an untrusted environment – like a public cloud – while retaining confidentiality of both the model and the data.

Nevertheless, TEEs have a number of limitations stemming from the underlying technology that shields the TEE application from any other (privileged) code running on the same host. Namely, the complexity of the encrypted runtime memory subsystem poses limitations on the size of the runtime memory that TEEs can use. Earlier versions of Intel SGX allowed up to 128MB of encrypted runtime memory. Upcoming version will allow several GBs of encrypted runtime memory, but will not provide any integrity – probably allowing attacks that may leak memory contents [46].

Relevant parameters for TEE used in AI application include:

- Size of the runtime memory. This parameter determines the size of AI network that can be instantiated within a TEE. In case the memory requirements of the application are higher than the memory allowed by the TEE, practitioners may have to design their application as a distributed application by using several TEE instances. Spanning the application across several TEE instances may also be necessary to cope with dynamic data loads. Frameworks to scale TEEs have been proposed in the past [47].
- Storage freshness. TEEs provide encrypted and authenticated storage through a so-called “sealing” interface. Yet, the interface provides no freshness and a malicious operating system may provide the application with stale storage. This malicious behavior is known as “rollback attack” that is a special instance of so-called “forking attack” [48]. Solutions for storage freshness have been proposed, but are currently not available in the cloud. The availability (or lack) of storage freshness may affect the design of the AI application.

Secure Multi-party Computation

Secure multi-party computation (MPC) enabled two or more parties to jointly compute a function over data that is private to some or all of the parties. Classical examples of multi-party computation include a two-party protocol to determine which party holds the largest value while keeping each value secret, or a two-party protocol to determine the intersection between two private sets, each provided by one of the parties. MPC is based either on so-called garbled circuits [49] or on secret-sharing [50]. A number of proposals leverage MPC for AI applications, both for training and testing purposes [51], [52], [53]. In a nutshell, the network is treated as a function to be computed over the input data and this is carried out via an MPC protocol. Note that also the function parameters (i.e. the network hyperparameters) can be kept private.

Relevant parameters for AI applications based on MPC are:

- Number of involved parties. MPC protocols do not scale well with the number of parties involved in the computation. While, in principle, MPC can be generalized to accommodate for arbitrary number of parties, faster schemes are designed for two-party scenarios
- Number of communication rounds. MPC protocols require the parties involved in the computation to be only throughout the protocol execution and this may span across several communication rounds. Alternatively, MPC based on secret-sharing could leverage two (or more) servers that run the MPC protocol on behalf of the parties that provide the data. This means that data providers only have to send shares of their private data to the servers and can later go offline. However, this approach requires the server not to collude, i.e., if the servers running the MPC protocol collude and join the shares they have received from data providers, privacy is lost.
- Adversarial model. MPC protocols consider either semi-honest or malicious parties. A semi-honest party abides to the protocol specifications (yet, it may try to infer private information from its protocol view) whereas a malicious party can act arbitrarily (e.g., send malformed/arbitrary messages). MPC protocols that withstand malicious adversaries exhibit larger overhead compared to protocols for the same functionality that can only provide security in presence of semi-honest adversaries.

3.3.2 DISCUSSION OF TRADE-OFFS

The above study of privacy-preserving methods reveals a number of trade-offs that should be considered in the evaluation. In other words, methods for preserving privacy incurs cost in certain aspects such as the utility of the data and the accuracy of an analysis on the data. In this section, we take a step back from individual methods and provide a higher-level view of the trade-offs that is observed across multiple methods.

- **Privacy vs. Accuracy**

In both differential privacy and federated learning, we see an impact on the accuracy of the result. As differential privacy mechanisms add noise to the original data and the anonymity increases as more noise is added, the accuracy is likely to be degraded by greater noise. Similarly, federated learning inevitably sacrifices the accuracy of the ultimate model. It trains the model with a limited amount of the data that is available at the moment of a particular round. As privacy protection in principle requires certain type of filtering or modification of the data, it is likely that such a trade-off is observed in privacy protection methods in general. This suggest that a primary evaluation metric for a privacy preserving method is to quantify this trade-off, the degree of privacy protection and the impact on the accuracy of the model or data.

- **Privacy vs. Resources**

As observed in Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) and Multiparty Computation (MPC), a privacy protection solution is built upon a special software or hardware environment. For example, TEE requires a memory and storage space specifically developed for the application and MPC involves a distributed set of nodes that participate in the computation and communications between them. In federated learning, since the ultimate model is trained over

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a series of training iteration, it not only involves communication costs from the end-devices but also it takes time for having the model.

- **Privacy vs. User experience**

We also find that a privacy solution can have an impact on user experience. As observed in the case of federated learning, a privacy solution can involve end-devices (e.g., smartphones) that directly interact with users. In federated learning, involving end-devices is crucial and inevitable since it protects privacy by keeping the data in users' devices. As such it incurs overhead at the end-devices, i.e., computation of the local models and communication of the local and global models, and it consumes computation power, memory, and energy of the devices. Therefore, an important aspect to understand and measure regarding the related parameters (e.g., the number of rounds, hyperparameters of the local models) is the impact on user devices and the experience of the user.

4 PROPOSAL OF METRICS

4.1 METRICS FOR ACCOUNTABILITY

As aforementioned in Section 3.1.1, general approaches to achieving accountability focus on understanding of how an AI system works. It involves the **transparency** in all processes, including data collection, data processing, modelling choices, training quality and releasing source code, as well as the **explainability** of the used AI models (e.g., the quality and the comprehensiveness of the explanations). In other words, the main goal of the accountability metrics is for assessing different aspects of **transparency** and **explainability**. In this section, we propose a number of metrics for general cases and, if applicable, further analyse them for AI-based systems.

Accuracy:

In general, accuracy is a metric that measures the fidelity and/or soundness of an explanation toward an AI system by determining how 'accurate' or how well the explanation matches underlying system processes. Below is a simple expression for determining an accuracy value by letting LS be the number of correct statements regarding the underlying process and NLS , conversely, is the number of incorrect statements, or statements that have no corresponding link to the process [54]:

$$AC = \frac{LS}{LS + NLS}$$

In AI systems, accuracy involves different processes, namely:

- Data sampling: In an AI-based monitoring system, accuracy may refer to how accurately the monitoring data is sampled and measured.
- Data collection: E.g., the accuracy can be related to the packet loss ratio.
- ML algorithm: A number of accuracy-related metrics for evaluating the ML algorithm [55] are listed below.
 - Classification Accuracy
 - Logarithmic Loss
 - Confusion Matrix

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- Area under Curve
- F1 Score
- Precision and Recall
- AUROC (Area under Receiver operating characteristics curve)
- Mean Absolute Error
- Mean Squared Error
- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE),
- R^2 (R-Squared) Coefficient of determination

Timing/ Currentness:

Generally, timing or currentness is measured as the interval of time between something happening in the system and the system's providing information about it [54]. In AI systems, it includes the time consumption of all computations needed for the ML algorithms. If the AI system is for detecting the occurrence of an event, the metric can be measured as the time between the commencements of the event and the moment when the alarm is triggered.

Effectiveness/Detailing:

In general, this metric is used to measure whether a piece of information given to a user is detailed enough for answering the most relevant (important) questions regarding a process (e.g., What? Who? Why? When? To whom? Which?) and if it is effective enough to provide a general understanding of its subject [54]. For example, the provider of the AI solution may have to inform users of a system regarding how it collects and stores their data, who has access to this data and when/if it will be deleted. The effectiveness/detailing metric D is the percentage of important details provided to answer these important questions. For a piece of information, the detailing metric $D = d/P = 1 - u/P$. Here d denotes the number of answered questions, u denotes the number of unanswered questions and P denotes the number of important questions to be answered. For a set of n_I pieces of information, D is calculated as expressed in the following equation:

$$D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_I} d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_I} P_i^D} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_I} u_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_I} P_i^D}$$

Readability:

The readability metric measures the level of ease for a user to read and understand a specific piece of information. In the context of XAI, if the piece of information is a text-based explanation, the readability can be calculated based on the average sentence length ASL (i.e., average number of words per sentence) and the average word length AWL (i.e., average number of syllables per word). For instance, a frequently used readability metric is the Flesch reading ease (FRES) [57] which is simplified as expressed in the following equation [54]:

$$FRES = 206.835 - (1.015 \times ASL) - (84.6 \times AWL)$$

The readability metrics R can be normalised as follows:

$$R = 0 \text{ if } FRES < 0$$

$$R = \frac{FRES}{100} \text{ if } 0 \leq FRES \leq 100$$

$$R = 1 \text{ if } FRES > 100$$

Accessibility/ Availability:

Generally, the availability of a service reflects how easy it is for a user to use or to access the service. In terms of XAI systems, this metric can be measured based on the number of interactions (e.g., typing, clicks, taps, slides, etc.,) or steps needed to reach the explanation. The availability obtains the maximum value 1 when no interactions/ steps are required.

Complexity:

In AI systems, this metric measures the level of ease for understanding the used ML models. A simple way of quantifying complexity on a structural basis would be to count the number of components and/or interactions within the system or the ML model. For example, some low-dimensional classifiers (e.g., decision trees or naïve Bayes-based channel state prediction models) could directly be explained by their processing logic. However, models with complex structures, like deep neural networks or SVM-based optimizing models, are hard to explain due to complex multilayer connections or hyperplanes [59].

Confidence:

Different XAI methods may give us different results or different explanations. To increase the degree of confidence of applying different XAI methods, we need to define some metrics to assess the quality of their explanations. We discuss three metrics to answer the following questions [1]

- **Consistency:** Do different XAI methods produce similar explanations on average?
The **Consistency metric** compares different XAI methods and evaluates them to see how close the explanations are to each other, for example by calculating an average distance between the explainability methods. If different XAI methods lead to similar results, this would mean a higher degree of confidence can be placed in using them. If not, we would need to carefully interpret the explanations of each method to identify which one is the best.
- **Stability:** Are the explanations similar for similar instances?
The **Stability metric** evaluates the similarity between different instances under two criteria: those instances must be close in the feature space and have similar outputs. If instances are similar, we would expect the respective model output for these instances to be similar as well. Therefore, this metric allows for building trust in a specific explanation.
- **Compacity:** Do a few features still drive the same model?
The **Compacity metric** seeks to reduce complexity and overexplaining by measuring the explainability of a decision in relation to only the most important features. For each instance, after identifying feature importance using XAI methods, we select a subset of features with the highest contributions and observe how well they approximate the model.

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All three aforementioned confidence metrics can be calculated using Shapash [60], which is an open-source Python library aiming to make machine learning interpretable and understandable by everyone.

4.2 METRICS FOR RESILIENCE

There are two main approaches to evaluate the resilience of a system against attacks: 1) to assess the effectiveness of its defense at mitigating attacks, 2) to assess its vulnerabilities and the effectiveness of attacks against it. The former approach assumes there are defenses deployed against attacks, while currently most ML systems do not deploy any specific defense against adversarial ML attacks. Yet different ML systems provide different level of resilience. The evaluation of vulnerabilities is more generic and it applies to any ML system, even those which do not deploy defenses. Thus, we will focus on computing a resilience score based on vulnerability assessment to measure the resilience of ML systems.

For the sake of completeness, we shortly cover approaches to evaluate the effectiveness of defenses and provide some example metrics that can be used for this purpose. These are generic metrics which apply in a similar manner to any attack against ML system. For instance, we can adapt existing resilience metrics defined for the resilience of cyber-physical systems [61] to ML-based systems. Some of these metrics are depicted in Figure 2 and defined as follows:

- **Performance (or resilience) loss** corresponds to the difference between the normal performance of the system and its performance under attack. For an ML system, it would typically be an accuracy metric or a measure of expected business outcomes.
- **Absorb Phase Time** corresponds to the time required for the defense approach to start working, during which the attack impacts the ML system.
- **Recover Phase Time** illustrates how fast the ML system can recover to its original performance.

FIGURE 2. DEPICTION OF PHASES DURING THE DEFENSE AGAINST AN ATTACK AND THEIR IMPACT ON SYSTEM PERFORMANCES.

The definition of our resilience metrics based on vulnerability assessment is guided by the popular CVSS framework and its *severity score* for vulnerabilities, which is computed as a combination of *impact* and *exploitability*:

$$\text{Severity Score} = \text{Roundup}(\text{Minimum}[(\text{Impact} + \text{Exploitability}), 10])$$

$$\text{Impact} = 6.42 \times (1 - [(1 - \text{confidentiality}) \times (1 - \text{integrity}) \times (1 - \text{availability})])$$

$$\text{Exploitability} = 8.22 \times \text{AttackVector} \times \text{AttackComplexity} \times \text{PrivilegesRequired} \times \text{UserInteraction}$$

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Exploitability considers several parameters depicted in Table 1, of which attack *complexity* and *privileges required* are the most interesting parameters for our evaluation of ML system resilience.

TABLE 1. COMPONENTS OF EXPLOITABILITY FOR A VULNERABILITY, THEIR POSSIBLE VALUES AND ASSOCIATED SCORES.

Exploitability	Values	Scores
Attack vector	Network - Adjacent - Local - Physical	0.85 - 0.62 - 0.55 - 0.2
Attack complexity	Low - High	0.77 - 0.44
Privileges required	None - Low - High	0.85 - 0.62 - 0.27
User interaction	None - Required	0.85 - 0.62
Scope	Unchanged - Changed	affect other scores if changed

We propose to quantify the resilience of an ML system based on four characteristics that quantifies the severity of its vulnerabilities. Each characteristic is represented by a metric that must be computed using empirical evaluation of the vulnerabilities against a given adversarial ML attacks:

- **Impact** quantifying the effect of the attack on the system from an integrity, availability or confidentiality perspective. A high impact decreases resilience.
- **Complexity** quantifying the effort required by an attacker to achieve a successful attack. A high complexity increases resilience.
- **Detectability** (of the attack exploiting the vulnerability) quantifying the effort required by a defender to detect and mitigate an attack exploiting the vulnerability. A high detectability increases resilience.
- **Capability** (privileges) required, quantifying the capabilities required by an attacker to achieve the attack. High required capabilities increase resilience.

We give examples metrics that can be used to quantify each of these characteristics for resilience against poisoning, evasion and model stealing attacks.

- Resilience against Poisoning Attacks

The resilience against poisoning attacks must be evaluated using a State-of-the-Art poisoning attack, e.g. [62], that is executed against the ML system in the most realistic setting possible. Based on this empirical evaluation, the following resilience metrics can be computed.

Impact can be empirically quantified as the difference between the original accuracy of a benign ML model F compared to the accuracy of the compromised model F_p after a successful poisoning attack. This accuracy is computed on a pre-defined test set. Several accuracy metrics like *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall*, *AUC* or *F1-score* can be considered to evaluate this accuracy drop. One must select the most relevant metric according to the ML model purpose. A better metric than accuracy decrease is the relative increase in error between F and F_p . It better depicts the relative decrease in performance with respect to the original ML model performance. Several error metrics like *FP rate*, *FN rate* or $(1 - F1\text{-score})$ can be considered here again and impact can be computed as follows:

$$Impact = \frac{Error(F_p) - Error(F)}{Error(F)}$$

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Complexity can be quantified using the ratio of poisoned data D_p in the final poisoned training dataset $D + D_p$, which also includes benign data D . The more data required to poison an ML model the more complex the attack.

$$Complexity = \frac{|D_p|}{|D + D_p|}$$

Detectability can be computed in several manners by quantifying how different the poisoned data in D_p is, from the data in D . Methods to detect out-of-distribution samples based on their input or output distribution (with respect to a benign ML model) can be used for this purpose [63] [64]. Methods specifically designed to detect poisoned samples can also be used [65] Using this detector, the detectability of a given poisoning attack can be computed as the ratio of detected poisoned samples over the total number of poisoned samples in D_p .

$$Detectability = \frac{|Detected(D_p)|}{|D_p|}$$

Capability is more difficult to quantify in a linear manner because adversarial capabilities are typically binary. In the case of poisoning attacks, we identify three main capabilities namely *label flipping*, *data injection* and *data modification* (+ any combination of those). Providing a score for each of these capabilities will depend on the context of an ML model in deployment and to its attack surface. An expert must rank these different capabilities and give each of them a score much like the scores are given to *privileges required* in the CVSS scoring system for None, Low and High privileges: 0.85 – 0.62 – 0.27.

- Resilience against Evasion Attacks

The resilience against evasion attacks must be evaluated using a State-of-the-Art evasion attack, e.g.[66], that is executed against the ML model in the most realistic setting possible. Based on this empirical evaluation, the following resilience metrics can be computed.

Impact can be empirically quantified using the attack success rate. It is computed as the ratio of adversarial examples X_a , generated from X , being successful at evading their target ML model F . The original samples used in this empirical assessment to generate adversarial examples must be selected at random to obtain a relevant impact score. This equation exemplifies how it would be computed for an untargeted evasion attack:

Complexity will be quantified differently for different capabilities. In *white box* attacks, complexity can be quantified as the computation (CPU/GPU usage), time or memory required to generate an adversarial example. In the *black box* setting, providing only query access to the ML model, complexity can be quantified as the number of queries required to generate a successful adversarial example. Once again, these values must be averaged over several generated adversarial examples and complexity can be computed this way:

$$Impact = \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{x_a \in A} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } F(x_a) \neq F(x) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Detectability can be computed by quantifying the modifications required to generate an adversarial example successful at evading its target ML model. For instance, the distance between original X and adversarial examples X_a , computed as an L_p norm, can be used to quantify detectability. In order to get a more representative score, this distance can be scaled

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using a constant depicting the maximum allowed modification ε and it must be averaged over a large set of adversarial examples A .

$$Complexity = \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{X_a \in A} \#queries(X \rightarrow X_a)$$

Alternatively, methods to detect out-of-distribution samples based their output distribution, with respect to the target ML model, can also be used for this purpose [63] [64]. In such case, the detectability can be computed in the same manner as for poisoning attacks. Also, for *black box* attacks, detectability can be computed as a function of the number and type of queries required to generate an adversarial example. The more queries required, the easier the attack is to detect.

$$Detectability = \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{X_a \in A} \frac{\|X_a - X\|}{\varepsilon}$$

Capability has to be again quantified in a discrete manner because adversarial capabilities are discrete. In evasion attacks, capabilities will relate to ML model access. The maximum capability is *white box* access, which is full access to ML model. The minimum capability is *black box*, which is only query access to the ML model, with different granularity of access to responses, e.g., label only, confidence score, etc. In between these two capabilities, there are many “*grey box*” capabilities providing different information about the ML model, e.g., training data, ML model type, training algorithm, etc. Providing a score for each of these capabilities will depend on the context of an ML model in deployment and its attack surface. Nevertheless, capability scores should respect this hierarchy *white box* > *grey box* > *black box*.

- Resilience against Model Stealing Attacks

The resilience against model stealing attacks must be evaluated using a State-of-the-Art model stealing attack, e.g. [31], [32], that is executed against the ML model in the most realistic setting possible. Based on this empirical evaluation, the following resilience metrics can be computed. **Impact** can be quantified by evaluating the fidelity of the surrogate stolen ML model in copying its target. Depending on the attacker goal, either accuracy or agreement between original ML model F and surrogate stolen ML model F' can be computed to estimate the impact. When considering model agreement, impact is computing as follows using a reference test set D :

$$Impact = \frac{1}{|D|} \sum_{x \in D} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } F'(x) = F(x) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Complexity can be quantified as the number of queries required to build a stolen surrogate ML model F' reaching the desired performance (accuracy or agreement). The more queries required, the more complex the attack.

$$Complexity = \#queries(F')$$

Detectability can be computed in a similar manner as for poisoning and evasion attacks, by detecting out-of-distribution samples based on their input or output distribution (with respect to the ML model). Methods specifically designed to detect and mitigate model stealing attacks can also be used [33]. Using either detector, the detectability of a model stealing attack can be computed as the ratio of detected queries over the total number of queries Q generated to steal the model.

$$Detectability = \frac{|Detected(Q)|}{|Q|}$$

Capability is similar to *grey box* and *black box* for evasion attacks. *Black box* is only query access to the ML model, with different granularity of access to responses, e.g., label only, confidence score, logit values, etc. *Grey box* capabilities provide increasing information about the ML model, e.g., surrogate/real training data, ML model type, training algorithm, etc. Providing a score for each of these capabilities depends on the context of an ML model in deployment, on its attack surface and it must be determined by an expert. Capability scores should respect the hierarchy *grey box* > *black box*.

4.3 METRICS FOR PRIVACY

In this section, we propose the metrics regarding the privacy aspects of ML systems based on the analysis of the trade-offs in Section 3.3.2. The metrics are proposed specifically in the context of the use case of task 1, “Edge computing platform for running privacy-preserving AI methods”, that will be implemented in work package 5. Meanwhile, we also discuss how they can be translated for wider use cases.

- User Diversity

This measure is proposed to understand the degree of privacy or anonymity an ML system is achieving. The measure should quantify the diversity of the users participating in an ML system or a data set, and specific to the use case of Task 5.1 (Pilot on edge computing platform for running privacy-preserving AI methods) the measure could provide the demographic distribution such as gender or age-group and the types of devices the users hold. This is analogous to providing summary statistics in data sets made with differential privacy mechanisms.

- Risk of privacy exposure

Regarding the same goal of understanding the degree of privacy or anonymity, another directly related metric is the probability of privacy exposure, for instance, the parameter ϵ of differential privacy. Since a metric for this risk is inherently specific to a particular ML model, type of inference made by the model, and attack scenarios, we give a few examples that can be practically used as metrics in different scenarios.

While we gave how the ϵ is defined in Section 3.3.1, there are tools that aid ML developers to employ differential privacy in their data, and specify the desired level of ϵ (e.g., Opacus [67], Tensorflow privacy [68]). ML Privacy Meter [69] provides a tool for empirically quantifying the risk privacy leakage regarding membership inference attacks.

- Performance (as an instance of utility)

This is a typical measure to understand the trade-off of a privacy solution with respect to the utility of an ML system. While the utility of an ML system is defined depending on the task, we here use the accuracy as the measure of utility, which is common in classification or regression tasks. More importantly, the metric should be also computed for the ML system which does not employ a privacy mechanism so the cost of the privacy solution can be understood by comparing the difference of the performances.

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- CPU consumption

Our study of the privacy solutions suggests the importance of understanding the overhead incurred to user by a privacy solution. The CPU consumption is a metric that captures one aspect of such overhead. We believe this could be measure both in-lab and in-the-wild experiments. An in-lab study would allow an accurate measurement of the overhead under controlled settings whereas a real-world experiment could additionally acquire the subjective evaluation of users about the impact of the overhead on their user experience.

- Battery consumption

This is another metric with which shares the same objective of understanding the overhead incurred to end users. As there are privacy solutions that involve battery-powered mobile devices (e.g., federated learning), the degree of energy consumption becomes important. Again, the consumption could be measured in an in-lab setting for an objective measure, and also through a real-world experiment to gather subjective experience of the users.

- Time consumption

Lastly, time required for obtaining a quality ML model is an important aspect for understanding the trade-off of a privacy approach. Considering a federated learning model, training the model takes multiple iteration and takes longer time eventually. The time aspect not only affects the users but also the ML service provider. The time for training the model can be measured and compared for different settings, for example, between a centralized setting and a distributed setting.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The ultimate goal of this deliverable is to propose metrics for understanding the trustworthiness of ML systems. In order to achieve the goal, we first unfold the three key areas that consist of the trustworthiness namely, accountability-explainability, resilience, and privacy. For each of the area, the deliverable provides an overview of approaches and identifies the factors/parameters involved, and the trade-offs. This overview established a basis for the discussion of the necessary metrics. We then propose a set of metrics for each area, that reflects the parameters and trade-offs and also the use cases of SPATIAL, which will be developed in the future.

The study we conducted and the metrics proposed for the three areas is pertinent to the entire SPATIAL project as it sets detailed objectives for the upcoming tasks and use case development. The metrics of each area suggest the specific goals that an ML system should target to satisfy. In addition, as the proposed metrics cover various aspects within each studied area, they can serve as a framework for profiling ML systems from multiple perspectives, which will ultimately contribute to raising awareness on the trustworthiness of AI systems and giving detailed directions for achieving it.

The contributions of this deliverable will be vital for later tasks of the SPATIAL project. As for the immediate next task of proposing a process for integrating the metrics to AI development (task 2.3), it sets the target that the process should be aim at. More importantly, the metrics lay a basis for evaluating the all the development efforts included in the tasks of work package 3

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and work package 5. The metrics will also serve as crucial elements for the overall evaluation of the SPATIAL project, and the communicating the results. Since the exploration conducted in this document and the proposed metrics go beyond the specific uses in SPATIAL and use cases, they will also serve as a firm basis for future AI trustworthiness initiatives.

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